

SPATIAL ANALYSIS OF THE HEALTH INFRASTRUCTURE IN CITY OF JALANDHAR USING REMOTE SENSING AND GIS

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ABSTRACT

The paper examines the distribution of health infrastructure in Jalandhar city, Punjab, India. It also examine the different types of existing health facilities in city. This paper also identify the total number of different kinds of health centers that comes within the city. Additionally the paper also analyze the spatial assessment of health centers in Jalandhar city with the help of remote sensing and GIS till year 2020.

The paper also reveals the different categories of health centers in Jalandhar city in the State of Punjab at the city level.

This paper also assess the present status of availability of the health infrastructure in Jalandhar city.

KEYWORDS – Health Infrastructure, Remote Sensing and GIS

INTRODUCTION

Health infrastructure is one of the major social infrastructure. As indicated by WHO, wellbeing is a condition of complete physical, mental and social prosperity and not only the shortfall of sickness or illness. A sound health is a condition of being well as well as mental and physical prosperity which is inevitable to live a beneficial, productive and healthiest lifestyle. Individual's development is depends on the healthy and long solid life. Consequently, the state of being well has become a significant for the advancement of human being. The facts confirm that a health wise solid individual is a resource for himself and for the development of economy as well. In order to accomplish the sound health and great wellbeing as far as, the nation ought to work on the establishment of the medical centers and also advancements of the health care facilities.

India has accomplished an extensive advancement in giving the health infrastructure facilities and also provides its accessibility to health administrations to the human beings. In most recent twenty years, in India, the health facilities has expanded and rectified many times. However, the health infrastructure is not properly distributed. Dibyendu Ghosh and Soumyananda Dinda (2017) have done a study on health infrastructure and economic development in India. They wrote about the various kinds of health care facilities and also about health infrastructure in India. They also talked regarding the life expectancy at birth rate as well as infant mortality rate depends on the health facilities. In the paper, they found out that the development of the healthy facilities improves the quality of life in India. Particularly, the two states Bihar and Uttar Pradesh are not developed much

as compared to the other states of India and these two states need more consideration to improve the quality wise health infrastructure as well as the distribution of the availability of health facilities. Ayodeji Makinde et. al. (2018) have done a study on the distribution of health facilities in Nigeria: implications and options for universal health coverage. In their research paper, they talked about the health amenities distributed in Nigeria and also about the quality wise health care facilities for the people. They have utilized the secondary investigation about the information from the Federal Ministry of health's facility in order to get the accessibility of dispersed health facilities in Nigeria. They found out that there are more primary health facilities than the secondary and the tertiary ones and also the government health facilities are much more than the private health facilities. Sarwar Jahan and Toshikatsu Oda (2000) have done a study on the distribution of public facilities in Dhaka, Bangladesh: a spatial analysis. They have used the method spatial analysis and they found out that the some wards and Thanas are much more evolved in terms of an exclusive convenience. Nevertheless, others lagging behind the mean level of advancement of the urban area in terms of the facility. Jahangeer Afzal Parry et. al (2017) have done an examination on locational investigation of ration depots in Jammu and Srinagar urban centers Jammu and Kashmir, India. They have used the technique like GIS. They found out that the status of the existence of the facilities more than that of the city as a whole, however the other thirty two wards which means the 47% have scarcity in the system of the formulization of the ration stores. Dilip saikia (2014) have done a study on health care infrastructure in the rural areas of north – east India: current status and future challenges. In this research paper they have talked about rural provincial medical services framework in India and health status in North – east India. The research paper is rooted on the auxiliary information. Different sources like bulletin on national health profile 2011 and rural health statistics 2011 have been utilized in order to gather the information. They found out that there has been essential increment in the health care facilities of countryside as well as health centers in the area.

Social infrastructure is necessary to accomplish the objective of economic development, quality of life as well as social turn of events. Health infrastructure is very essential in the development of a country. The establishment of the different health centers are necessary for the development. The health center is an establishment in order to provide the treatment to the patient by experts, qualified and trained medical and nursing staff as well.

OBJECTIVE

1. To study the distribution of different sorts of health infrastructure establishments in Jalandhar city.
2. To examine the existing different kinds of health facilities in the city.
3. To identify the total number of different kinds of health centers in city.
4. To analyze the spatial assessment of health centers in Jalandhar city with the help of remote sensing and GIS.

DATA SETS

The data related to health infrastructure like distribution of numerous health centers collected from various organizations. However, its location has been collected using the Hand Held GPS of the hospitals in terms of government, charitable and private sectors. The information related to health facilities, different organizations like government as well as private departments has been consulted to provide the data. The Master plan report, Census report, Jalandhar map and detailed report of Jalandhar has been taken as the secondary data. Satellite imagery,

GIS software, Google earth imagery, demographic and administrative maps have been taken to map the distribution of health infrastructure in urban areas of the Jalandhar city.

PRIMARY DATA SOURCES

1. Georeferencing and digitization of the administration boundaries of India, Punjab has been done from published data on Bhuvan.
2. Georeferencing and digitization of the ward boundaries from the Jalandhar Municipal Corporation report has been done.
3. Identified GCPs/ Location Hospitals in terms of Government, Charitable and Private sectors and created point layers in ARC GIS Desktop 10.2.1.
4. Digitize/Import the pattern and distribution of health infrastructure on shape files and created maps.

SECONDARY DATA SOURCES

1. The inventories of the health centers has been obtained from Punjab Remote Sensing Center.

METHODOLOGY

To prepare the base map of Jalandhar city, Georeferencing and digitization of administration boundaries of India, Punjab has been done from published data on Bhuvan.

Georeferenced and digitization of ward boundaries from Municipal Corporation Jalandhar reports and also identified the GCPs/ Location using the Hand Held GPS of hospitals in terms of Government, Charitable and Private sectors, in order to locate the health infrastructure facilities.

STUDY AREA

Jalandhar city positioned at 31° 34' 48" N and longitude 75° 34' 48" E with an area of approximately 2632 km² and average elevation of 228 meters above mean sea level (748 ft.). The city is a sports hub and lies alongside the Grand Trunk Road and is easily accessible by well-established railway tracks and good roads. The Jalandhar is 144 km northwest of Chandigarh, which is the state capital of Punjab and Haryana and also one of the union territory of India. There are astounding medical centers and amenities in Jalandhar which incorporate treatment centers and hospitals with availability of experts and specialists. The Municipal Corporation of Jalandhar claims that the city has more than 423 medical centers, a case that will make it the city with the most elevated number of medical centers in South Asia. The state Punjab has become very urbanized in character as it is urbanizing quickly and its future is by all accounts metropolitan. With urbanization remaining at 33.95%, Punjab is positioned at fifth major urbanized province of India after Tamil Nadu with 43.86%, Maharashtra with 42.40%, Gujarat with 37.35% and Karnataka with 33.98% and it comes under most urbanized states in the northwest locale of the country. The level of metropolitan populace in Punjab has been on the ascent persistently.

National Highway 44 (old NH1) connects Jalandhar with Srinagar in the northern most part of India and Kanyakumari in the southern end of India (Kashmir to Kanyakumari)-a perpendicular transportation axis. En-route from Srinagar downwards, it connects Jalandhar with Jammu, Pathankot, Ludhiana, Ambala, Karnal and Delhi in the regional context. Through NH-3, Jalandhar is connected with Atari border, Amritsar, Adampur Airport, Hoshiarpur (Punjab), Kullu and Manali of Himachal Pradesh. NH-703 links Jalandhar with Nakodar, Jagraon, Barnala, Mansa and Sardulgarh. NH-703A links Jalandhar with Kapurthala, Sultanpur Lodhi, Lohian and Makhu. Thus, Jalandhar reflects convergence as well as divergence of road transport which makes it the ideal transport Hub. Similarly, Jalandhar city being located on the main junction of Jammu and Atari railway lines, is linked by this trunk route with major urban agglomerations of India namely; Jammu in the north, Kolkata in the east, Hyderabad, Chennai and Bengaluru in the south, Mumbai in the southwest, Ahmedabad and Jaipur in the west. It is also linked by railways with Nawanshahr, Hoshiarpur, Kapurthala, Firozpur and Sri Ganga nagar in Rajasthan.

Location Map of Study Area

Jalandhar City

Fig 1

Fig 2

DIFFERENT CATEGORIES OF HEALTH CENTERS

This paper reveals health facilities includes different types of hospitals and health centers in Jalandhar city. The different types of hospitals that includes private hospitals, charitable hospitals and government hospitals as well.

In addition to this, the paper also includes different categories of health centers that comes under Jalandhar city.

As per Clinical Establishment Act, 2010, the Allopathic hospitals are divided into different categories or levels. Level 1(A) includes the general medical facilities like nursing home, PHC etcetera run by MBBS Doctors. Level 1 (B) includes the specialist medical facilities provided by the Doctors from one or more basic specialties namely General Surgery, General Medicine, Obstetrics & Gynaecologist and Dentistry, Paediatrics that provides the OPD and indoor facilities.

Health infrastructure – it includes government health center, private health center and charitable health centers.

Fig 3

STATUS OF AVAILABILITY OF HEALTH FACILITIES IN JALANDHAR CITY

Jalandhar city, over some stretch of time, has risen as one of the greatest specific center points of clinical consideration in India as well as in South Asia.

The health centers and hospitals are the establishments that provides the therapy, facilities, services, treatment, and care to the patients by qualified, experts and trained staff. Hospitals have the facility to admit and care for the inpatients. However, the other health centers treat as day care centers. The general hospital, may have various departments to deal with numerous sorts of illness and injury, and it normally has an emergency department to deal with emergency and urgent cases.

According to a recent report, The Tribune, Jalandhar has emerged as Asia's biggest medicare hub. In Jalandhar city, there are numerous kinds of hospitals like eye hospitals, hospitals for thyroid patients, kidney hospitals, ENT hospitals, hospitals for heart patients. There are some hospitals that are the specialized one like trauma centers, children's hospitals, Mental hospitals and some hospitals are for special treatments like psychiatric problems. There are also IVF centers in the city. For the purpose of medical research, there are some hospitals which are affiliated with universities. These hospitals provide the trainings to nurses and physicians. Such hospitals are called teaching hospitals. There are one hundred fifty five private hospitals in Jalandhar city. There are the specialized hospitals in the city such as The Caremax hospital for heart patients, kidney hospital, Thind eye hospital, Golden hospital for thyroid patients, Kataria - Eye, ENT hospital, Apex hospital and maternity home.

There are five charitable hospitals in the Jalandhar city like Guru Nanak mission hospital, SGL charitable hospital, Arya Samaj charitable hospital, Devi Talab mandir charitable trust, Doaba charitable trust and there is one PHC or government hospital that is Civil hospital.

FIG NO. 4. SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF HEALTH INFRASTRUCTURE FACILITIES

Total Number of Hospitals in Jalandhar City

CONCLUSION

In before going discussions, it has been noticed that the Jalandhar city has the more existing healthcare facilities as Jalandhar has emerged as the Asia's biggest medicare hub. It is therefore safe to conclude that Jalandhar city is providing good health infrastructure.

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